

The Extent, To Which the Adoption of Information System in CRM Directly Benefits Customers, Improves the Performance and Increases Life Time Value of Any Organization. Case study: Haykal Hospital Laboratory

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Thesis Abstract

The aim of the study is to investigate and identify the present results of using CRMS in Haykal Laboratory and to insure the importance of the direct benefit from CRMS by customers. The first part of the study review literature covering what CRMS is and its effects on customers' life value in any organization and specifically in the health sector. These two parts of the review show that there is a growing need and demand for CRMS in all organizations. Then, the study explains how the usage of CRMS in laboratory provides staff with beneficial data which helps the manager to work on improving their decisions through viewing, thus understanding, customer's needs in order to meet their demands and needs, as well as, reach customer's long-life value. The study focuses on the benefits of CRMS usage in the laboratory which effects customers directly. An interview was done with the section director of the laboratory and questionnaires were distributed to staff and clients. Results are drawn by using frequency tables, pie charts, T-sample Tests and ANOVA tests through SPSS. In conclusion, the study proves that the usage of CRMS in a laboratory is essential and effective; however, the laboratory and hospital performance alongside with the customer's direct benefit cannot be expected to improve significantly without connection of the CRMS within the various departments of the hospital, as their clients are actually patients in the hospital.

Keywords: *customers' satisfaction; Sustainability; improvement; customers' life value; Data*

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

It is essential for any organization, whether a public or semi-public sector, to fully comprehend its customers. Experts and theorists like Thompson (2006) said: "CRM can be categorized into four groups: the strategy, the technology, the process system, and the Information System where many experts have been focusing on the importance of CRM concerning the idea of technology and information in order to focus on the Information System requirements. Technology refers to the computing capabilities that allow an organization to collect, analyze, trend, organize, save, and process data

about its customers. Information-technology based systems enable CRM systems to achieve their objectives of collecting, classifying, saving, and processing valuable data pertaining to customers. Combining information technology-based systems allows organizations to develop better relationships with customers by providing a wider outlook of the customer behavior." Throughout the previous decades, business improvement had been insignificant due to the lack of recognition and utilization of knowledge regarding customer behavior and needs within a product or service which provides predictions, based on the analysis of the computed customer-related information, regarding the organization services and productivity. Developing such a product was the primary and most important challenge in the business world. However, the business world nowadays is working more on every detail that pertains to customer satisfaction. Since the profitability of any organization is related to long life of customers, organizations focus on the customers and their loyalty from specific points that assist and ensure the sustainability of the organization. An organization's knowledge and its point of view regarding customers has improved tremendously due to the advancement of information that can be collected and processed, which has been embedded into the CRM System. CRM was initially serving as a ledger and productive front office which then improved to be a method to impel effective decisions regarding the collected data. The last phase of CRM development, which is the latest improvement is not only used as a referent to create decisions, but also as a platform to further understand and analyze the collected information according to the understanding of customers' needs and behaviors. Therefore, a CRM System (CRMS) is a combination of CRM in an organization and the System used to collect information, select necessary data, and analyze it. Furthermore, organizations understand the importance of managing customers' information due to the high competition in the market; thus the (CRMS) has become one of the most important solutions in order to gain competitive advantages. CRM permits the top manager to reshape the organization in order to achieve customer satisfaction and loyalty and increase customer life value.

Nowadays, the absence of CRM in an organization or misusing-it will slow down the success

of the organization—in the economy, since CRM catches the basic characteristics of an organization that leads to profitability continuously and sustainability of the business. CRM with the Information System is used to follow up work and facilitate daily basis operations when needed. CRMS gives the ability to make efficient and productive relationships with customers and especially direct relationships in order to maximize customers' life value and understand their prediction about the product. Implementation of CRMS allows the smooth passage of customer information through the concerned department. For granted, the information collected will allow the organization to understand their customer's needs in order to give them the service that meets their expectations with high life value. Expected service is a main part since many organizations, hospitals and laboratories use CRMS to increase work performance of their organization while customers are not affected directly which, obviously might not increase life value and loyalty for the organization. This is why it is important to make direct relationships and direct solutions for customers.

This study will show how CRMS has positive effects on handling conflicts and direct benefit for customer in order to reach satisfaction and increase customers' life value. Therefore, the study will be divided into several parts related to Customer Relationship Management: its concept, importance, goal, and how the System affected CRM positively in order to work on a strategy to prevent the failure of the businesses. It will also show the effects of Information System on CRM in an organization. In service sectors, CRM implantation improves the level of services, optimizing the cost, interaction with customers, and builds long relationship through direct solutions for customers in order to increase satisfaction, loyalty, and willingness to repurchase, as well as and neglect bad word of mouth.

1.2 Research Problem:

In the health industry we can find two categories; some do not believe in the usefulness of CRM and its involvement on customers' long-life value, and others who believe in it, but miss-implement it, therefore will not benefit from its efficiency. The main character of CRM in laboratories is the information system which consists of different information collected in order to consider customers' needs. Laboratories should increase the usage of information System in CRM in order to control the flow of information related to customers, by then it will improve meeting the needs and demand of customers and allow customers to benefit directly thus, increase satisfaction and loyalty.

The problem presented in this study:

To what extent does the absence of an Information System in CRM hinder direct benefits for customers, achieving goals, retention of customers, satisfaction and loyalty, and life time value in laboratories?

1.3 Research Objectives:

This study has the following objectives:

- State the importance of CRM in service industry.
- Explain how Information System can improve the performance of CRM.
- Explain how CRMS adoption develops the customer satisfaction and loyalty.
- Show the effect of CRMS implementation on long life value.

1.4 Research Questions:

Question 1: How does CRMS improve the performance of an organization and specifically laboratories?

Question 2: How does the implementation of an CRMS effect CRM performance in order to serve as a bridge between customers and the organization?

Question 3: How does CRMS affect satisfaction and loyalty?

Question 4: How does CRMS affect the long-life value of the organization?

1.5 Study Hypothesis:

This study aimed to build a relation between CRM with an Information System (CRMS) and customer loyalty in order to increase life value. The main point of this relation is to have efficient communication, understand customers' problems and needs, and handle conflicts in order to raise trust, satisfaction, and loyalty of customers which effect directly the quality of performance which lead to long life value.

Hypothesis 1

Alternative hypothesis: The implementation of CRMS in hospitals will have a positive effect on CRM performance to take the best decision and handle conflict.

Hypothesis 2:

Alternative hypothesis: The implementation of CRMS concept will have a positive effect on customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Hypothesis 3:

Alternative hypothesis: The adoption of CRMS concept will have a positive effect on long life value.

3.4 Research Model variables:

This research tries to show the effect of Information System on CRM adoption.

The model of this study considers the variables in this study are divided to two categories:

Independent variables:

Dependent variable:

- Customer data collected CRMS
- Understanding customers' needs
- Recover decisions
- Customer satisfaction & loyalty
- Life value

Figure 1: Research Model Variables

Chapter Two: Literature Review

Chapter 2: Literature Review:

2.1 CRM: Customer Relationship Management and its Importance

CRM is a direct concept, but there are many different definitions and implementations of CRM. In general, research problem solving of CRM focuses that CRM is not a marketing strategy, it is an organization strategy that refers all departments of the organization. Pokharel, B. (2011) said: “CRM is a process for acquiring, retaining, and growing customers. CRM is an

abbreviation for customer relationship management, not customer relationship marketing. Management is a broader concept than marketing because it covers strategic management, human resources management, marketing management, service management, knowledge management, sales management, research management and development management; any type of management in any organization. Thus, CRM requires organizational and business level approaches, which are customer centric, to do business.” Hence, there is misunderstanding regarding CRM importance and its benefits. Researchers as Ibrahim (2015) paid more attention that CRM strategy is a business strategy to identify a service organization’s most profitable customers and prospects, and devotes time in order to increase operation of each customer through time. This point of view will reach its goal only when organizations believe that CRM is an organization strategy not marketing department strategy.

In the existing literature, we find several definitions for the (C.R.M.) which describe it and show the main aspects of CRM. (Khoshraftar & al.2011) mentioned that CRM is an innovative System which facilitates the process to acquire, develop, and maintain customer relationships more efficiently and effectively. CRM is an approach for any organization to learn the maximum about their customers and their prospects, to communicate relevantly, reduce time information, and track results to make program adjustments as necessary. The power of CRM is the smooth passage of information through all departments of the organization. The relation between departments and information create improved decisions for each manager in order to improve the decision of the organization overall. Ibrahim & al (2015) and Greenberg (2009) explained that the relation between CRM and marketing departments is to benefit lately from the good relationship with customers. Having good relation with customers can be through good communication, ability to provide solution to their conflicts, and direct benefit through the CRMS used. Even though many researchers focus on CRM and marketing department, but they know that this enabling to follow-up sales and marketing activities, which leads to gain a competitive advantage and makes the customers the center of attention and the primary point in the organization which cannot be done without the connected information commencing all departments. It is very significant to spotlight that the aim of CRM as an organizational strategy is to sustain long term relationships to fulfill customers’ needs. When the organization reaches a number of satisfied customers, then, loyalties increase, customer profitability increases. Therefore, Hung (2015) mentioned the importance of having correct information to store and use correctly

when needed to reduce wasted time through the operation of each customer. As explained before, the main aspect of CRM is customers' data collected which must be gathered swiftly.

In the previous decades, usage of CRM was very poor and slow, but after the development of a System it rapidly increased its benefits and focused on its importance and relation. Combining the concept of CRM with advanced information technologies produces the CRM systems that are known as Information System packages, which lead to mixing and coordinating the business processes that deal with customers. Laudon K.C. and Laudon J.P. (2006) clarified that the combination of technology with CRM improves the benefit of CRM usage and facilitates it among all departments.

All organizations have expanded and have faced high competition locally and globally. Therefore, attracting new customers and sustaining the organization, were very hard issues. Regarding this point of view was CRM creation and development in order to have a solution with the development of organizations. Many service businesses such as banks, insurance companies, and laboratories realize the importance of CRM according to its direct effects on customers. Ibrahim & al (2015) explained that CRM helps in capturing new customers, retaining existing ones, and maximizes their life time value. Therefore, close relationships with customers require a strong coordination between information technology and all departments of the organization to reach customer long life value. Peng & al. (2012) articulated that in order to better satisfy the needs of their customers, many companies are performing substantial changes and transformations in their organizational culture, structure, and business processes, from the traditional product-oriented style to a more customer-oriented one. Reddy and Acharyulu (2002) believe that "CRM is the establishment, development, maintenance, and optimization of long-term mutually valuable relationships between customer and organization."

Focusing on the importance of CRM might be explained by researchers as a combination of people and system in order to understand customers and specific marketing activities. Almotairi (2009) for example focuses on the most important objective and said: "The main objective of CRM is to translate the customer information into customized products and services that meet the changing needs of customers in order to gain their loyalty." Regarding to the impact of CRM System on internal process and learning and growth dimensions, many researchers like Reimer and Becker (2015), Chathoth (2007) and Olsen & Connolly (2000) argued that, the effective usage of Information Systems will

improve productivity and service quality, as well as help in decreasing the potential for service errors and recovery costs associated with such errors. This improvement will increase customer satisfaction and loyalty (Jayachandran; 2004).

CRM does not stand only in the stage of buying and selling a service, actually it is a way of action done in order to retain newer customers, sustain the previous ones, and to reach customer loyalty level. Jagdish and Paravatiyar (2001) mentioned CRM in their book: "CRM emerging concept tools and applications," explained CRM as a: "Comprehensive strategy and process of acquiring, retaining, and partnering with selective customers to create superior value for the company and the customer. Through its capability to collect, store, refine, analyze, and disseminate customer information within organization, CRM System enables the organization to improve organization ability to attract and retain current and potential customers." Therefore, we can say that good implementation of CRM comes from gathering valuable customer data to provide solutions to them and increase the quality of the decision-making process taken by the organization. High quality of decision-making improves the relationship between organization and their customers which develop the interaction between them. Good relations give the organization the ability to listen to the customer, analyze the needs, notes, and feedback given by them. Therefore, development of customer satisfaction and loyalty leads to long term customers.

Collecting more data is not about making work flow easily only, but it is to increase knowledge and improve decisions which allow customers benefit from the organization directly. This benefit starts from predicting what customers might need. Prediction enables organizations to drive new insights or new information from existing ones. Therefore, the first step is to collect the maximum quantity of information possible, then, identify which information or data is relevant for the purpose.

CRM systems are widely perceived as one of the main strategic tools to enable and facilitate these fundamental business changes in organizations. A CRM system is a way of vision and an organization culture that stands to improve the organizational activities toward customers. This is done through believing that the improvement of organization performance starts first by building good relationships with customers. Since, customer relations in an organization goes through pre-purchase, purchase, and post-purchase, it is important to imply the linking of CRM processes with the customer life-cycle concept, since researchers defined CRMS as the activities performed by the organization concerning the management of the customer relationship, grouped

according to a longitudinal view of the relationship" (Santouridis and Tsachtani 2015). Regarding the organizational strategy, objectives and vision, all must be updated according to the CRMS and customers' needs in order to sustain and increase long term value.

Regarding the characteristics of CRM that helps organizations to understand their customers' needs, Greenberg (2009) said that the main objectives of CRM implementation are to reshape the culture, structure, and process of the organization. Almotairi (2010) articulated in his PhD thesis that they have defined CRM as "the strategic process of shaping the interactions between a company and its customers with the goal to maximize the lifetime value of customers for the company, as well as to maximize satisfaction for the customer." CRMS is a method which is used to improve customer communication, customer retention, customer loyalty, and customer profitability through understanding and customer behavior regarding the organization.

Productive CRMS mostly is shown through the organization performance and understanding customer's needs to improve customer's relation, who are expected to be solicitors for the organization in their society. Bruce et al (2015) defined CRMS as "the process that identifies customers, creates customer knowledge, builds customer relationships, and shapes customers' perceptions of the firm and its products/solutions. CRMS was often defined as a form of relationship strategy". Therefore, we can conclude that CRMS is not one objective; it's a collection of objectives and tools that belong in all areas of an organization to enable and facilitate the fundamental business changes as Greenberg; Hussein et al and M Viljoen et al (2005) explained. Ibrahim et al and many other researchers focus on the importance of having an efficient relationship between customers and their choice of organization in order to increase productivity. Many researchers like Bruce, Reimer and Becker (2015), Jayachandran (2004), Hung (2015) and others clarify that CRM helps organizations to collect data, analyze, and manage customer related information through the use of an information system. Understanding customer needs increases satisfaction of customer and establish loyalty and long-life value. The biggest business challenge that an organization has to face is the challenge of convincing customers to trust the organization and its product. Maintaining and increasing customer loyalty level is essential for any service company's long-term success. Creating a conceptual frame work for the CRM system using multivariate measurement system, such as factor analysis or principal component analysis, yields an improvement in business by increasing the level of customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. (Khoshraftar & al.2011)

In the healthcare sector it is more specific and personal since customers there are patients and the product finally is their health. Therefore, a CRM package's importance is to lead to higher satisfaction of patients and their demand, build strong relationship in order to give the hospital their personal data without hesitation, and reduce time spent on serving each patient. Researchers provided that the CRM strategy which should be acquired is to build trust of their patients in order to help them elude feeling alienated in the healthcare environment and simultaneously improve the service quality and the efficiency of healthcare. Regarding the healthcare sector, Arora (2003) stated in her article that "a good relationship between organization's providers and its customer does not only improve customers' satisfaction, but also CRM helps in fostering effective communications between them, which may help to improve their health and health-related quality of life which will help increase effectiveness of chronic disease management."

Over time, organizations have noticed that creating or retaining new customers might be simpler in respect to the trait of many people who like to try anything new, while maintaining and sustaining existing customers is complicated and more important in order to build long life value. Therefore, an organization must identify the most valuable customers, and increase customer loyalty by providing customized products and services. According to Alkhazali and Hassan (2015) and Bruce & al (2015), CRMS is seen as strategy that gives priority in the decision-making process and serves as an essential tool for most business firms that are working towards creating a long-term and rewarding interaction with their customers.

We can bring to a close that CRM is vital in various aspects, from re-shaping the organization, culture, strategy to implementing a process in order to capture new customers, retain existing ones and maximize their life time. The combination of strategy and information system improves the organization process to provide better products and services even after selling. As a conclusion, CRM enables the organization, through its entire department scoped on re-focusing on customers' needs, behaviors and developing predictions for the company related to product and service, to improve the overall performance of the organization.

All these aspects are essential for the improvement of CRM in order to reach loyalty and long-life value. Over all read researches, an important aspect was missed, which is direct benefit and usage by customers to the CRMS. This aspect will improve understanding

customers' needs, satisfaction, and loyalty and increase customers' life value. When customers directly feel that the organization is interested in their comforts and needs, they will be an advocate for it and reject any negative confrontations. The research of Kotler and Keller (2009) noticed that some indicators of customer loyalty are willingness to keep buying the product or service over a long, willingness to do positive word-of-mouth, and Willingness to propose an idea for the organization to develop the product or service. Pokharel, B. (2011) mentioned that the quality of customer data, un-skilled people, and misusing of customer data by organization are challenges that faced organizations during the phase of implementing CRM and might reach to the failure of the organizations.

Therefore, we can conclude that CRM system can be considered as one of the important organization's resources that can be used to improve overall performance. Explicitly, previous studies contended that CRM System has a positive and significant impact on customer perspective (Alkrouch et al., 2011). Chan, J.O. (2005) mentioned that CRM is a combination of strategy and information system aimed at focusing attention on customers in order to serve them better. An integrated business model that ties together business organizations, processes, information and technologies along the entire value chain is critical for the success of CRM strategies. Managing and analyzing customers' information allows us to understand generally about the society, thus attracting new customers and retaining existing one. CRMS decreases the errors and improves productivity and quality, analyzes documents, and generates solutions for problems smoothly and speedily Therefore successful CRM is to manage customers and have the ability to listen to them and understand their needs. The aspect of understanding customers' needs is about the influence that we can reach with customers which positively affect customer relationship quality and duration. This influence might increase when customers feel and benefit from the organizational performance in order to serve them better and having the readiness to handle customers' conflicts.

2.2 History of CRM:

The CRM life cycle is initiated with the combination of an organization's system and the flow and needed customer information. According to Billey (2015), in the distant past all companies were operating by means of "The Ledger": The humble paper pad and pen which allowed businesses to track basic sales and customer information. In the 1950s, The Rolodex style was implemented. This style depended on the spangle desk accessory of a million executives. The Rolodex

offered companies the ability to spin through paper records, adding customers while updating existing customer information, details and more.

In the early 1980s, Database Marketing was created. This new process allowed companies to build up and analyze customer information, enabling businesses to create customized communications to attract prospects. In the Late 1980s, Software was established as Contact Management Software which was the arrival and mass rollout of PCs and server/client architecture through which businesses were collecting and organizing customer data into what were effectively digital Rolodexes. The net result though was clunky, limited insights into customers and company interactions with them while Rosenfield (2002) mentioned that the promise of database marketing was to speak individually to countless customers. The reality was that it was too costly, too difficult, and didn't pay out on the bottom line, except in the case of business-to-business key account marketing. One could benefit simply by knowing how recently and frequently customers purchase; how much they spend; what they purchase; and an idea of demographics. Almost everything else was fluff and gloss. After 2000s researchers explained how CRMS is a necessary program for any organization regardless its size which is important for the process, development, profitability, and reducing mistakes and time of information through relevant communication with customers and smoothly passage of needed information.

Chapter Three: Research Methodology

3.1 Study area (Laboratory of Haykal Hospital)

Haykal is a hospital that provides medical services to patients. It has only one branch; it came into existence in 1968.

3.1.1 History and background of HAYKAL

The idea of establishing HAYKAL dates to 1968. "Haykal Hospital" was established as an organization dedicated for providing quality health care to patients of North Lebanon and other regions all over the world. In year 2000, after which Haykal Hospital had put tremendous effort and time, Haykal opened the Obstetrics Gynecology department and developed new premises for the Operating Room. In 2005, the Neonatal Intensive Care unit was founded. Through the year 2008, new promises for the Medical Archive department and high-tech theatre room were in progress.

3.1.2 Goals of HAYKAL

According to Haykal Hospital they aim to:

1. Meet patients and partners expectations
2. Improve the efficiency and quality of care
3. Optimize economic efficiency
4. Ensure the ongoing adequacy of the activities and resources

3.1.3 Why Haykal Laboratory?

After searching through 12 hospitals' laboratories in Tripoli and nearby, only Haykal laboratory has the service of online tracking of results which permits their customers to take their results online, signed and ready for any governmental usage, without going to the laboratory.

10 hospitals don't have even online results which are:

- Monla hospital
- Mazloum Hospital
- Salam Hospital
- Tripoli Governmental Hospital
- Hanan Hospital
- Orange Naso Hospital
- Islamic Hospital

- Bisar Hospital
- Lebanon Heart Hospital

- Chahin Hospital

While Nini Hospital has the tracking online result, however the results are not ready for governmental usage, rather they are for doctors or personal information only. Therefore, the study is done regarding Haykal laboratory. Haykal Laboratory strives to perform all laboratory examinations using equipment directly related to the system in order to directly benefit from the CRMS. As of now, all departments in the laboratory are connected to the system except for one due to the cost and space needed to acquire the CRMS compatible model of the device. The latest application developed, which highlights the performance of CRM system in the hospital overall and the laboratory specifically, is the "hospital laboratory results online tracking", where customers can acquire their results online, ready for any formal usage without going to the

laboratory, oriented to provide customer efficiency and convenience especially for those reside far from the hospital.

3.2 Research Instrument

Explanatory research: It is utilized to study a specific situation in order to explain a relation among variables that scopes more beneficial results.

The results of explanatory research can provide significant insight into a given situation which is usually useful for decision-making by any organization. Although the results of qualitative research can give some indication as to the "why", "how" and "when" something occurs, it cannot tell us "how often" or "how many" times. Explanatory research is not typically generalized to the population at large.

Probability and Non-Probability Sampling

In general, researchers prefer probabilistic or random sampling methods over non-probabilistic ones, and consider them to be more accurate and rigorous. However, in applied social research there may be circumstances where it is not feasible, practical or theoretical. For the purpose of this research, a questionnaire was the research instrument used for data collection. The research is based on purposive sampling. The study will address the employees, customers, and the laboratory department. One of the first things to do is to verify that the respondents do, in fact meet the criteria for being in the sample. Purposive sampling can be very useful for situations where you need to reach a targeted sample quickly and where sampling for proportionality is not the primary concern. With a purposive sample, one should get the opinions of our target population (employees and the customers).

3.2.1 Questionnaire

For the quantitative part of the survey, as part of the primary data collection, questionnaires were handed out to HAYKAL's 19 employees and to 45 clients. The aim was to understand the employees' and the clients' perspectives and acquire insights into their satisfaction with the hospital services. Also, to scope the effect of implementing CRM system within the hospital and can

evaluate the impact of such an implementation on employees' performance and clients' satisfaction. Additionally, the questionnaire aims to get employees' and clients' opinions on the performance of the CRM system regarding applying CRM principles, and the extent it facilitates their work. The questionnaires were distributed to the targeted individuals and they were requested to return it within few days. The time allotted was set in order to provide them with enough time to think their answers through before responding and to reduce the natural resistance in answering freely.

3.2.2 Interview

An interview is a main part of the study since it is usually done with a highly responsible person in the organization. In the study, an interview was done with the section director of the laboratory Dr. Malak Nabulsi. For the interview, nine questions were prepared. The interview was done in order to understand the director's perspective and vision pertaining to maximizing customer satisfaction and retaining new customers. The interview aimed to understand the workflow of CRMS in the laboratory from the entrance of customer until he receives his results. The interview attempts to note the laboratories perspective regarding customers and CRMS in order to improve the laboratory performance and increase customer satisfaction and loyalty.

3.3 Reliability and Validity of Instruments

Easterby-Smith (2008) defines reliability as the extent to which data collection techniques or analysis procedures will yield consistent findings. The primary objective should be that if a later investigation followed exactly the same procedures as described by an earlier investigator and conducted the same study all over again, this later investigator should be able to arrive at the same results and conclusions. However, due to the very nature of human beings 100% reliability cannot be considered for this study, as individual perceptions and feelings are central in this study. In other words, because we are different as individuals and that our preferences and perceptions are different, future investigations may not produce exactly the same results as reported in this thesis. Nonetheless, this study's results could be regarded as quite reliable.

The research for this thesis could be considered as a field research as it is carried out among people who constitute the work force and who can have opinions and answers which were not be influenced in any manner. Furthermore, to

ensure both internal and external validity, the right and relevant questions were asked in the survey, the most feasible data collection method was used, and the tools used to analyze the data are also considered to be accurate and produce valid results. Thus, the overall validity of this thesis is considered to be high.

3.6 Data Collection Methods

The study placed heavy emphasis on using formulized standard questions and predetermined response options.

The study has targeted a large mainstream from different levels and positions, in the objective to gather accurate information about the implementation of CRM system. Also, in the questionnaire there are meaningful questions developed to collect insights into the relationship that exerts between appropriate implementation and staff performance. Most respondents at HAYKAL enjoy professionalism and objectivity, so the questionnaire was designed to cover all the aspects mentioned in the introduction and literature review in order to cover a large spectrum of CRM practices at various levels.

Questionnaires were distributed to the employees and customers by hand via direct interaction as a method to ensure maximum representation from the employees that are implementing the CRM system and that are interacting directly with the clients to avoid any possible biases. A total of 27 questions were set, 17 questions were target to the laboratory department and 10 to the clients,

Both quantitative and qualitative approaches complement each other by bringing width and depth into the research. A combination of both approaches was ascertained as ideal for determining the research questions. The combined approach is meaningful in order to explore the subject in depth and assess the importance and impact of CRM system in the hospital. The major part of this thesis uses both the quantitative and qualitative method, as the aim is to focus on gathering information or opinions about the various factors in a systematic manner.

An interview was done with the Sector Director of the laboratory by asking 9 prepared questions. The aim of the interview is to understand the application used in their laboratory, why the laboratory decided to track it, how the laboratory workflow occurs, and if using CRMS improves the performance of the laboratory and increases

loyalty and satisfaction level of customers. The questions and its answers will be mentioned in addition to its analysis in the next chapter.

Methods of Data Collection

- Questionnaires with closed-ended questions were distributed among employees, clients, and to the laboratory department of the hospital.
- Interview's questions were opened-ended questions.

Concerning Haykal laboratory, no one had previously written or made a research about implementing CRM in it and its impact on the relationship between the laboratory and its clients.

3.7 Data Processing and Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data for this research work. Descriptive statistics typically summarize data to make it simpler to interpret, and present it in a more manageable form. The interpretation of the results from the survey (questionnaires) will be visualized mainly via pie charts, a descriptive table, a correlation table, a T- sample test, and an ANOVA test in order to clearly envision the responses. A deductively-based analytical procedure is done by explaining a previous theory regarding CRM systems and obtaining information from research studies to ensure that any organization would be significantly less efficient without good application of the CRM system. Afterwards, the findings are used to create theories and to come up with a conclusion.

3.8 Summary

This chapter presents the research philosophy, design and methodology for this explanatory study. This study is a case study of HAYKAL in North Lebanon. The unit of analysis is the employees, the clients, and manager of the laboratory. The embedded units of analysis are the CRM principles that should be implemented at the hospital.

The research design includes the following strategies:

- A literature survey to investigate factors which promote CRM
- A research questionnaire distributed to HAYKAL Laboratory employees.
- An interview with the Section Director of the laboratory.

Two formal instruments were used to measure the employee and clients' satisfaction or frustration, namely the employee questionnaire (Appendix A) and the clients' questionnaire (Appendix B). The data retrieved from the employees and clients' survey was automatically generated by the SPSS program. The data was coded and transformed using pie charts from the SPSS program. SPSS was used to produce full statistical distributions, in a pie chart format, descriptive table, correlation table, T- sample Test, and an ANOVA test, of all the indices and variables which contributed to the results founded. Indicators of or lack of implementation a CRM system in the laboratory were calculated by accumulating contributing variables and calculating the extent of implementing CRM practices or not.

The findings from the employees and the clients' questionnaire are presented in chapter *Chapter Four: Data Presentation and Analysis*

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the data collected from the employees and customers results from conducting interviews and handing out questionnaires. A CRMS questionnaire can be used for several purposes. A combination of information is to gauge whether employees in the laboratory apply this system and are trained on it. Such questionnaires test the employee's knowledge and application on this system, as well as when they started working in the laboratory.

A different form of CRM questionnaire can be used to gauge employees' satisfaction with the job environment and technology, the workload, and salary among other things that enhance employee performance. Based on the data collected in such surveys, the top management of the laboratory would be able to formulate systems that could considerably reduce any weaknesses that may hamper employee performance and customer satisfaction.

4.2 Reliability Test:

A measure of reliability should be defined by business requirements in the form of service levels. These requirements should then be used to measure test results and the overall reliability metric of system under test. This test is signed by Cronbach alpha.

The Cronbach alpha coefficient is an index generally used to determine the consistency of all psychological tests. The Cronbach's alpha can take several values, from 0 to 1. The more the result is close to 1, the more it will show higher level of internal consistency. A Cronbach's alpha value comprised between 0 and 0.50 reflects insufficient reliability, between 0.50 and 0.70 acceptable reliability, and between 0.70 and 1.0 high or very high reliability. The questionnaires were presented to an expert and they were determined to be counted on. In the following table, the Cronbach alpha resulted with a 0.7, which is considered high in the north of Lebanon, regarding that Haykal laboratory, according to its CRMS application, improved its CRMS performance. The 0.7 result shows very good reliability level that effect positively on CRM performance in decision making and handling conflict.

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.700	14

Table 1: Employees' Reliability Statistics

Customers' results:

In the following table, the Cronbach alpha resulted with a 0.704, which is considered high in the north of Lebanon, regarding that Haykal laboratory, according to its ITS application, improved its CRMS performance. The 0.704 result shows very good reliability level that effects positively on the environment of customers' satisfaction and loyalty and also has a positive effect on long life value.

Reliability Statistics

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.704	8

Table 2: Customers' Reliability Statistics

4.3 Descriptive Statistic:

4.3.1 Frequency Table & Pie Charts of Employees:

Sex of Employees

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	1	5.3	5.3	5.3
Valid Female	18	94.7	94.7	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

Despite the fact that there are 23 employees at Haykal Laboratory excluding the top manager and his assistant, the table reflects only 19 of them due to the remaining four female employees being on vacation. The table and chart indicate that there is a deficit in the gender of employees, about 95% of them are females and 5% only

are males. Furthermore, most the employees requested for an increase in employees in order to expedite the processing of the workload as well as reduce stress because they reason that the workload given to them surpasses their capability.

Age of Employees

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid <30	6	31.6	31.6	31.6
Valid <50	12	63.2	63.2	94.7
Valid <70	1	5.3	5.3	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

According to the table and chart below most of the employees (63.2%) are less than 50 years, 31.6% are less than 30 years, while only 5.3% of them are between 50 and 70 years old.

This is favorable for the laboratory and the hospital overall. The results shown indicate that most of the employees are feasible with the technology and that there are no worries about any training to be done for them

Years of Work

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
New	4	21.1	21.1	21.1
>2	2	10.5	10.5	31.6
>5	4	21.1	21.1	52.6
>7	9	47.4	47.4	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

Both employees who had been working between 7 and 5 years and those who were new had the same percentage 21.1% while those who had been working there more than 7 years are the majority 47.4%. Less than 2 years workers are the least percentage 10.5%.

From these answers we can know if there were any improvements or training or recognition of employees' performance etc... during their working years.

Income of Employees

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Below average	3	15.8	15.8	15.8
Average	15	78.9	78.9	94.7
Above average	1	5.3	5.3	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

Most of employees 78.9% believe that their income is among the average and feel satisfied regarding their performance. This gives the hospital high rank among hospitals through the income satisfaction. The rest are divided between below and above average. Only one person said that his income is above average 5.3% while

15.3% feel unsatisfied and believe that their income is below average according to their job. This result will help us to recognize the level of satisfaction of employees in order to distinguish the reasons for unsatisfied ones.

Does the Hospital provide all necessary systems and equipment for you to complete your task successfully?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
DS	2	10.5	10.5	10.5
N	3	15.8	15.8	26.3
S	6	31.6	31.6	57.9
SS	8	42.1	42.1	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

About 26% combined between dissatisfied and neutral. Those who are not satisfied argue that they need more technology to facilitate their work which is still done manually, while 31.6% are satisfied and 42.1% are

strongly satisfied. These results show that even in the same laboratory, there are some departments which need more technological equipment which will increase the CRMT.

Have you received any training on the CRM system before starting to use it?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid SDS	1	5.3	5.3	5.3
DS	2	10.5	10.5	15.8
N	2	10.5	10.5	26.3
S	7	36.8	36.8	63.2
SS	7	36.8	36.8	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

About 26% of employees mentioned that they did not receive any or sufficient training on CRM system while 74% have trained on it. This result may be a result

of having new employees or other employees that were trained but did not understand the combination of new technology in their job and CRMS.

Can your daily tasks be achieved without the use of CRM system?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid SDS	4	21.1	21.1	21.1
S	8	42.1	42.1	63.2
SS	7	36.8	36.8	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

21% of employees are not satisfied by the CRMS and they suggest that their tasks could be done and achieved without the CRMS. 79% of employees are divided between satisfied and strongly satisfied. This indicates that the majority understands the CRMS importance and it is probable that those unsatisfied with their work are out of the system.

Do you think that CRM system facilitates data collection of your customers?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid SDS	1	5.3	5.3	5.3
N	2	10.5	10.5	15.8
S	9	47.4	47.4	63.2
SS	7	36.8	36.8	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

5.3% of the employees were strongly dissatisfied while 10.5% were neutral about the facilitation of CRM System to collect data. 47.4% were satisfied and 36.8% were strongly satisfied. The 15% of the employees

who are not satisfied might be due to misunderstandings in the importance of CRMS as the majority assure its facilitation in data collection of customers.

Do customers give you all the requested information easily and without embarrassment?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid DS	1	5.3	5.3	5.3
N	6	31.6	31.6	36.8
S	10	52.6	52.6	89.5
SS	2	10.5	10.5	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

5.3% of employees strongly disagree that customers inform them requested information. 31.6% reported that it is neutral. 52.6% were satisfied and only 10.5% were strongly satisfied and sure that customers give the

needed information easily. This result could be a sign of the extent that customers feel comfort towards the laboratory.

Do you frequently use data collected on CRM?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
N	4	21.1	21.1	21.1
S	7	36.8	36.8	57.9
SS	8	42.1	42.1	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

21.1% feel neutral towards the frequency of usage of the data collected while 78.9%, which is the majority, are

divided between satisfied and strongly satisfied. This might depend on the type of work for each employee.

Does the CRM allow you to categorize and identify relevant information for a particular purpose?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
N	6	31.6	31.6	31.6
S	4	21.1	21.1	52.6
SS	9	47.4	47.4	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

47.4% were strongly satisfied and 21.1% were satisfied that CRMS allows categorization for relevant information, where 31.6% felt neutral. This result shows that unsatisfied employees are zero, therefore the

variation in their answers differs according to the type of work

Does the CRMS usage allow you to reduce the number of errors?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
DS	1	5.3	5.3	5.3
N	2	10.5	10.5	15.8
S	10	52.6	52.6	68.4
SS	6	31.6	31.6	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

According to the chart and the table it is shown that 31.6% are strongly satisfied with the CRM system ability to reduced errors while, 52.6% are satisfied and

5.3% are dissatisfied. 10.5% think that there is no relation between the CRM system and the reduction of errors.

Would you say that understanding your customers' needs increases the rate of return clients?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
DS	2	10.5	10.5	10.5
N	3	15.8	15.8	26.3
S	8	42.1	42.1	68.4
SS	6	31.6	31.6	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

According to the chart and table below, it can be noticed that most of the employees (73.7%) are among satisfied and strongly satisfied and agree that understanding their customers' needs increase rate of return clients, while 26.3% are among dissatisfied and neutral.

Do you think that CRMS is useful to improve employees' performance?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid SDS	1	5.3	5.3	5.3
DS	1	5.3	5.3	10.5
N	2	10.5	10.5	21.1
S	10	52.6	52.6	73.7
SS	5	26.3	26.3	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

The majority of employees (78.9%) in this table and chart shows that they think that CRMS is useful to improve their performance, while 10.5% don't think that there is any relation between CRMS and making

improvement to their performance. 10.6% are even dissatisfied or even strongly dissatisfied and believe that this concept has failed and it never affected their performance.

Do your customers support ideas for hospital services improvement?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid SDS	1	5.3	5.3	5.3
N	3	15.8	15.8	21.1
S	10	52.6	52.6	73.7
SS	5	26.3	26.3	100.0
Total	19	100.0	100.0	

78.9% (SS and S) are from the employees; as shown below in the chart and table; who think that customers

might support ideas for hospital service improvement, while 21.1% think that customers do not support ideas.

What do you think the management should do to help you handle work-related stress better?

Answers of this question differ according to their needs and responsibilities in the laboratory.

5% of the staff decided not to answer even though they were noticed about this question perhaps it was left by error. 11% are not satisfied by their salaries and think that they work deserve more based on their work. 16% of staff related their stress to the huge amount of work

which needs more daily staff to handle it. Another 16% mentioned that their job stress is related to the lack of space so their movement is limited, thus increasing their tension. The majority 53% explained that they have a department which is still manual, not linked to the system directly, due to the need of a new machine which necessitates more staff and space to put it.

What would you like the management to improve in order to motivate employees?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Rewards	1	5.3	5.6	5.6
Higher income	3	15.8	16.7	22.2
Both	14	73.7	77.8	100.0
Total	18	94.7	100.0	
Missing System	1	5.3		
Total	19	100.0		

In the chart and table below, we can notice that most of the employees (73.7%) would like their management to both increase salaries and give rewards in order to motivate them. The rest would be motivated with one incentive, either rewards or income increase.

4.4 Inferential Statistics:

Through this section, we examine whether the answers given to the variables' questions do considerably vary according to demographic factors such as age, income, years of work, system applied, and official form on the general questions and the new factors.

It contains explanation of the effect of these factors using statistical tests. In our case, the T-test is applied in order to compare the means and the ANOVA test is

applied whenever we need to compare the means of more than two groups.

According to the results of these tests, they are considered to reflect a significant difference if they display a Sig level inferior to the error rate (error ratio = 5%). Otherwise, the difference is considered to be insignificant.

4.4.1 One sample T-test:

It is a statistical procedure used to examine the mean difference between the sample and the known value of the population mean and make statistical decision as to whether or not the sample mean is different from the population mean

4.5 Employees' Result Analysis:

4.5.1 Employees' T-Test:

One-Sample Statistics

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
EAF1	Does the Hospital provide all necessary systems and equipment for you to complete your task successfully?	19	4.0526	1.02598	.23538	17.218	18	.000
EAF2	Have you received any training on the CRM system before starting to use it?	19	3.8947	1.19697	.27460	14.183	18	.000
EAF3	Can your daily tasks be achieved without the use of CRM system?	19	3.7368	1.52177	.34912	10.704	18	.000
EAF4	Do you think that CRM system facilitates data collection of your customers?	19	4.1053	.99413	.22807	18.000	18	.000
EAF5	Do customers give you all the requested information easily and without embarrassment?	19	3.6842	.74927	.17189	21.433	18	.000
EAF6	Do you frequently use data collected on CRM?	19	4.2105	.78733	.18063	23.311	18	.000
EAF7	Does the CRM allow you to categorize and identify relevant information for a particular purpose?	19	4.1579	.89834	.20609	20.175	18	.000
EAF8	Does the CRMS usage allow you to reduce the number of errors?	19	4.1053	.80930	.18567	22.111	18	.000
EAF9	Would you say that understanding your customers' needs increases the rate of return clients?	19	3.9474	.97032	.22261	17.732	18	.000
EAF10	Do you think that CRMS is useful to improve employees' performance?	19	3.8421	1.21395	.27850	13.796	18	.000
EAF001	Do your customers support ideas for hospital services improvement?	19	3.8947	1.14962	.26374	14.767	18	.000
EAF003	What would you like the management to improve in order to motivate employees?	18	2.5000	.98518	.23221	10.766	17	.000

Table 3: Employees' T-Test Result; N=19

One Sample T- Test Analysis:

EAF1:

Mean depression score ($M = 4.05$, $SD = 1.02$) was around or lower than the normal depression score of 4.0, $t(18) = 17.218$, $p = 0.000$.

EAF2:

Mean depression score ($M = 3.89$, $SD = 1.19$) was lower than the normal depression score of 4.0, $t(18) = 14.183$, $p = 0.000$.

EAF3:

Mean depression score ($M = 3.73$, $SD = 1.152$) was lower than the normal depression score of 4.0, $t(18) = 10.70$, $p = 0.000$.

EAF4:

Mean depression score ($M = 4.10$, $SD = 0.99$) was around or lower than the normal depression score of 4.0, $t(18) = 18.183$, $p = 0.000$.

EAF5:

Mean depression score ($M = 3.68$, $SD = 0.749$) was lower than the normal depression score of 4.0, $t(18) = 21.4$, $p = 0.000$.

EAF6:

Mean depression score ($M = 4.2$, $SD = 0.78$) was around or lower than the normal depression score of 4.0, $t(18) = 23.3$, $p = 0.000$.

EAF7:

Mean depression score ($M = 4.1$, $SD = 0.89$) was around or lower than the normal depression score of 4.0, $t(18) = 20.17$, $p = 0.000$.

EAF8:

Mean depression score ($M = 4.1$, $SD = 0.80$) was around or lower than the normal depression score of 4.0, $t(18) = 22.11$, $p = 0.000$.

EAF9:

Mean depression score ($M = 3.84$, $SD = 1.21$) was lower than the normal depression score of 4.0, $t(18) = 17.73$, $p = 0.000$.

EAF10:

Mean depression score ($M = 4.1$, $SD = 0.89$) was around or lower than the normal depression score of 4.0, $t(18) = 13.79$, $p = 0.000$.

EAF001:

Mean depression score ($M = 3.89$, $SD = 1.14$) was lower than the normal depression score of 4.0, $t(18) = 14.76$, $p = 0.000$.

EAF003:

Mean depression score ($M = 2.5$, $SD = 0.98$) was lower than the normal depression score of 4.0, $t(18) = 10.76$, $p = 0.000$.

Some Mean scores are equal to 4 or slightly greater; this might be due to the sample size. Even though, we have a statistically significant difference between means

($p < .05$), $p = 0.000$, thus, we can reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis

4.5.2 Employees' Correlation:

		EAF1	EAF2	EAF4	EAF5	EAF6	EAF7	EAF10	EAF001	EAF003
EAF1	Pearson Correlation	1	.457*	.103	.456*	.605**	.533*	.275	.382	.028
	Sig.		.049	.674	.049	.006	.019	.255	.107	.911
EAF2	Pearson Correlation	.457*	1	.290	.147	.437	.275	.217	.072	.525*
	Sig.	.049		.229	.549	.061	.255	.371	.769	.025
EAF4	Pearson Correlation	.103	.290	1	.718**	.183	.043	.337	.156	.152
	Sig.	.674	.229		.001	.453	.863	.159	.523	.548

EAF5	Pearson Correlation	.456*	.147	.718**	1	.401	.408	.186	.282	.040
	Sig.	.049	.549	.001		.088	.083	.445	.243	.876
EAF6	Pearson Correlation	.605**	.437	.183	.401	1	.500*	.444	.578**	.199
	Sig.	.006	.061	.453	.088		.029	.057	.010	.430
EAF7	Pearson Correlation	.533*	.275	.043	.408	.500*	1	.126	.232	-.068
	Sig.	.019	.255	.863	.083	.029		.607	.339	.789
EAF10	Pearson Correlation	.275	.217	.337	.186	.444	.126	1	.744**	-.167
	Sig.	.255	.371	.159	.445	.057	.607		.000	.507
EAF001	Pearson Correlation	.382	.072	.156	.282	.578**	.232	.744**	1	-.151
	Sig.	.107	.769	.523	.243	.010	.339	.000		.549
EAF003	Pearson Correlation	.028	.525*	.152	.040	.199	-.068	-.167	-.151	1
	Sig.	.911	.025	.548	.876	.430	.789	.507	.549	

Table 4: Employees Correlation

According to the table above there is correlation:

- Between EAF1 and EAF2 equal to 0.457 at a significant level of $0.049 < 0.05$.
- Between EAF1 and EAF5 equal to 0.456 at a significant level of $0.049 < 0.05$.
- Between EAF1 and EAF6 equal to 0.605 at a significant level of $0.006 < 0.05$.
- Between EAF1 and EAF7 equal to 0.533 at a significant level of $0.019 < 0.05$.
- Between EAF2 and EAF003 equal to 0.525 at a significant level of $0.025 < 0.05$.
- Between EAF4 and EAF5 equal to 0.718 at a significant level of $0.001 < 0.05$.
- Between EAF6 and EAF001 equal to 0.578 at a significant level of $0.01 < 0.05$.
- Between EAF6 and EAF7 equal to 0.500 at a significant level of $0.029 < 0.05$.
- Between EAF10 and EAF001 equal to 0.744 at a significant level of $0.000 < 0.05$.
- Training received on CRM system and how frequently usage of data collected with what the manager could to in order to improve employees' performance.
- How CRMS facilitate data collection and providing information easily by customers.
- Frequently usage of data collected, and categorizing relevant information
- Customers supporting ideas and usefulness of CRMS to improve employees' performance.

According to the correlation table we do not have any significant negative relation.

4.5.3 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA):

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) is an analysis tool used in statistics that splits the aggregate variability found inside a data set into two parts: systematic factors and random factors. The systematic factors have a statistical influence on the given data set, but the random factors do not. Analysts use the analysis of the variance test to determine the result independent variables have on the dependent variable amid a regression study.

The test allows comparison of more than two groups at the same time to determine whether a relationship exists between them. The test analyzes multiple groups to determine the types between and within samples. (investopedia.com). "When the variation of any quantity

There are positive relations between:

- Equipment and systems provided by the hospital and training on the CRMS, provide information easily by customers, frequently usage of data collected, and categorizing relevant information.

is produced by the action of two or more independent causes, it is known that the variance produced by all the causes simultaneously in operation is the sum of the values of the variance produced by each cause separately...The property of the variance, by which each

independent cause makes its own contribution to the total, enables us to analyze the total, and to assign, with more or less accuracy, the several portions to their appropriate causes, or groups of causes.”(isixsigms.com)

4.5.4 Employees’ ANOVA Test:

ONEWAY BY income

Descriptive

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Does the Hospital provide all necessary systems and equipment for you to complete your task successfully?	below average	3	4.0000	1.73205	1.00000
	Average	15	4.0667	.96115	.24817
	above average	1	4.0000	.	.
	Total	19	4.0526	1.02598	.23538
Have you received any training on the CRM system before starting to use it?	below average	3	4.3333	1.15470	.66667
	Average	15	3.8000	1.26491	.32660
	above average	1	4.0000	.	.
	Total	19	3.8947	1.19697	.27460
Can your daily tasks be achieved without the use of CRM system?	below average	3	2.0000	1.73205	1.00000
	Average	15	4.2667	1.03280	.26667
	above average	1	1.0000	.	.
	Total	19	3.7368	1.52177	.34912
Does the CRMS usage allow you to reduce the number of errors?	below average	3	4.6667	.57735	.33333
	Average	15	4.0000	.84515	.21822
	above average	1	4.0000	.	.
	Total	19	4.1053	.80930	.18567
Do you think that CRM system facilitates data collection of your customers?	below average	3	4.6667	.57735	.33333
	Average	15	4.0000	1.06904	.27603
	above average	1	4.0000	.	.
	Total	19	4.1053	.99413	.22807
Do customers give you all the requested information easily and without embarrassment?	below average	3	4.0000	1.00000	.57735
	Average	15	3.6000	.73679	.19024
	above average	1	4.0000	.	.
	Total	19	3.6842	.74927	.17189
Do you frequently use data collected on CRM?	below average	3	4.0000	1.00000	.57735
	Average	15	4.3333	.72375	.18687
	above average	1	3.0000	.	.
	Total	19	4.2105	.78733	.18063
Does the CRM allow you to categorize and identify relevant information for a particular purpose?	below average	3	4.3333	1.15470	.66667
	Average	15	4.1333	.91548	.23637
	above average	1	4.0000	.	.
	Total	19	4.1579	.89834	.20609
Would you say that understanding your customers’ needs increases the rate of return clients?	below average	3	3.3333	1.52753	.88192
	Average	15	4.0000	.84515	.21822
	above average	1	5.0000	.	.
	Total	19	3.9474	.97032	.22261
Do you think that CRMS is useful to improve employees’ performance?	below average	3	4.0000	1.73205	1.00000
	Average	15	4.0667	.59362	.15327
	above average	1	.0000	.	.
	Total	19	3.8421	1.21395	.27850
Do your customers support ideas for hospital services improvement?	below average	3	4.6667	.57735	.33333
	Average	15	4.0000	.65465	.16903
	above average	1	.0000	.	.
	Total	19	3.8947	1.14962	.26374

Table 5: Descriptive "by income"

ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1- Can your daily tasks be achieved without the use of CRM system?	Between Groups	20.751	2	10.375	7.930	.004
	Within Groups	20.933	16	1.308		
	Total	41.684	18			
2- Do you think that CRMS is useful to improve employees' performance?	Between Groups	15.593	2	7.796	11.409	.001
	Within Groups	10.933	16	.683		
	Total	26.526	18			
3- Do your customers support ideas for hospital services improvement?	Between Groups	17.123	2	8.561	20.547	.000
	Within Groups	6.667	16	.417		
	Total	23.789	18			

Table 6: ANOVA Test "By income"

By analyzing the given ANOVA table, we find:

- In the first question that the reported level of significance $p= 0.004 < 0.05$, implying that the relation between CRM technology and data collected (as a dimension) is highly significant and it is safe to use CRMT in order to improve performance of laboratory.
- In the second question, the reported level of significance $p= 0.001 < 0.05$ implying that the relation between CRM technology and taking the right decision through improving employee performance (as a dimension) is highly

significant and it is safe to use CRMT in order to improve performance of laboratory.

- In the third question, the reported level of significance $p= 0.000 < 0.05$ implying that the relation between CRM technology and satisfaction & loyalty through supporting ideas by customers for hospital service improvement (as a dimension) is highly significant and it is safe to use CRMT in order to improve performance of laboratory.

ONEWAY BY years

Descriptive

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Does the Hospital provide all necessary systems and equipment for you to complete your task successfully?	New	4	3.7500	.50000	.25000
	>2	2	3.5000	2.12132	1.50000
	>5	4	4.2500	.95743	.47871
	>7	9	4.2222	1.09291	.36430
	Total	19	4.0526	1.02598	.23538
Have you received any training on the CRM system before starting to use it?	new	4	3.0000	1.15470	.57735
	>2	2	4.0000	1.41421	1.00000
	>5	4	3.7500	1.89297	.94648
	>7	9	4.3333	.70711	.23570
	Total	19	3.8947	1.19697	.27460
Can your daily tasks be achieved without the use of CRM system?	new	4	4.0000	.00000	.00000
	>2	2	2.5000	2.12132	1.50000
	>5	4	3.7500	1.89297	.94648
	>7	9	3.8889	1.69148	.56383
	Total	19	3.7368	1.52177	.34912
Does the CRMS usage allow you to reduce the number of errors?	new	4	3.7500	.95743	.47871
	>2	2	4.5000	.70711	.50000
	>5	4	4.5000	.57735	.28868
	>7	9	4.0000	.86603	.28868
	Total	19	4.1053	.80930	.18567

	new	4	3.5000	.57735	.28868
Do you think that CRM system facilitates data collection of your customers?	>2	2	4.5000	.70711	.50000
	>5	4	3.7500	1.89297	.94648
	>7	9	4.4444	.52705	.17568
	Total	19	4.1053	.99413	.22807
	new	4	3.2500	.50000	.25000
Do customers give you all the requested information easily and without embarrassment?	>2	2	3.5000	.70711	.50000
	>5	4	3.5000	1.00000	.50000
	>7	9	4.0000	.70711	.23570
	Total	19	3.6842	.74927	.17189
	new	4	3.5000	.57735	.28868
Do you frequently use data collected on CRM?	>2	2	3.5000	.70711	.50000
	>5	4	4.7500	.50000	.25000
	>7	9	4.4444	.72648	.24216
	Total	19	4.2105	.78733	.18063
	new	4	3.5000	1.00000	.50000
Does the CRM allow you to categorize and identify relevant information for a particular purpose?	>2	2	4.0000	1.41421	1.00000
	>5	4	4.5000	1.00000	.50000
	>7	9	4.3333	.70711	.23570
	Total	19	4.1579	.89834	.20609
	new	4	3.7500	.50000	.25000
Would you say that understanding your customers' needs increases the rate of return clients?	>2	2	3.5000	2.12132	1.50000
	>5	4	4.0000	.81650	.40825
	>7	9	4.1111	1.05409	.35136
	Total	19	3.9474	.97032	.22261
	new	4	4.0000	.00000	.00000
Do you think that CRMS is useful to improve employees' performance?	>2	2	3.5000	2.12132	1.50000
	>5	4	3.7500	.50000	.25000
	>7	9	3.8889	1.61589	.53863
	Total	19	3.8421	1.21395	.27850
	new	4	3.7500	.50000	.25000
Do your customers support ideas for hospital services improvement?	>2	2	4.5000	.70711	.50000
	>5	4	4.0000	.00000	.00000
	>7	9	3.7778	1.64148	.54716
	Total	19	3.8947	1.14962	.26374

Table 7: Descriptive table "by years"

ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Do you frequently use data collected on CRM?	Between Groups	4.686	3	1.562	3.620	.038
	Within Groups	6.472	15	.431		
	Total	11.158	18			

Table 8: ANOVA Test "By years"

By analyzing the given ANOVA table, it is found that the reported level of significance

$p = 0.038 < 0.05$ implying that the relation between CRM Technology and Understand customers' needs and right

decision (as a dimension) is highly significant and it is safe to use CRMT in order to improve performance of laboratory.

4.6 Customers' Results Analysis:

4.6.1 Frequency Tables and Pie Chart of Customers' Questionnaires

sex of customer

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	22	48.9	48.9	48.9
Valid Female	23	51.1	51.1	100.0
Total	45	100.0	100.0	

According to the table and chart below we can consider that our sample is high-quality since 48.9% are male and 51.1% are female.

Age of customer

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid <30	16	35.6	35.6	35.6
Valid <50	20	44.4	44.4	80.0
Valid <70	9	20.0	20.0	100.0
Total	45	100.0	100.0	

According to the table and chart the customers are divided to 3 categories (35.6%) are less than 30 years, 44.4% are less than 50 years, while only 9% of them are between 50 and 70 years old. The variety of client age is a positive indication for the laboratory and the hospital

overall. The results shown means that the hospitals' customers are from different ages therefore, the laboratory is trusted and accepted from various categories of the society.

How frequently do you deal with the laboratory staff?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid First time	2	4.4	4.4	4.4
Valid Sometimes	12	26.7	26.7	31.1
Valid Mostly	16	35.6	35.6	66.7
Valid Always	15	33.3	33.3	100.0
Total	45	100.0	100.0	

According to the frequency table and chart below, the customers' laboratory differs among 4 categories. Customers who deal with the laboratory exclusively (always) or mostly are approximately equal, 33.3% for

those who deal always with it and 35.6% for those who mostly deal with it. 26.7% sometimes deal with the Haykal laboratory while 4.4% only of the sample is dealing with it for the first time.

Did the laboratory staff explain to you about the new online result tracking application?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid SDS	3	6.7	6.7	6.7
Valid DS	2	4.4	4.4	11.1
Valid S	14	31.1	31.1	42.2
Valid SS	26	57.8	57.8	100.0
Total	45	100.0	100.0	

According to the table and chart, the majority (88.9%) are divided to two types strongly satisfied and satisfied. Both were explained to them but this difference is

according to the acceptance of idea and the way they took the idea. 11.1% were divided to 4.4% dissatisfied and 6.7% strongly dissatisfied.

Would you provide the hospital easily all the personal information needed?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid SDS	1	2.2	2.2	2.2
DS	3	6.7	6.7	8.9
S	11	24.4	24.4	33.3
SS	30	66.7	66.7	100.0
Total	45	100.0	100.0	

According to the table and chart below it can be noticed that most of the customers 66.7% are SS and 24.4% are S to provide with ease all the personal information

needed for the laboratory. While 6.7% are DS and 2.2% are SDS because they think that the needed information is unnecessary to be given to the laboratory.

Are you satisfied with the new online result hospital tracking application?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid SDS	8	17.8	17.8	17.8
DS	4	8.9	8.9	26.7
N	7	15.6	15.6	42.2
S	17	37.8	37.8	80.0
SS	9	20.0	20.0	100.0
Total	45	100.0	100.0	

In this table and Pie chart it is obvious that satisfaction varies among customers. More than half of them (57.8%) are among satisfied and strongly satisfied by the new online result hospital tracking application. While

15.6% feel neutral of it, it might be a result of thinking it is unnecessary. 26.7% of them are even dissatisfied or strongly dissatisfied, possibly due to their poor knowledge of technology

Does the laboratory staff remind you about the date of tests that should be repeated?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid SDS	4	8.9	8.9	8.9
N	32	71.1	71.1	80.0
S	4	8.9	8.9	88.9
SS	5	11.1	11.1	100.0
Total	45	100.0	100.0	

71.1% said neutral and they depended that to their needless of repetition. While, 20% are divided among strongly satisfied and satisfied according to their trust if

needed. Only 8.9% were strongly dissatisfied because they think that this is not the laboratory job, it is the doctors.

Do you think that the laboratory staff provides convenient solutions for your inquiry?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid N	12	26.7	26.7	26.7
S	14	31.1	31.1	57.8
SS	19	42.2	42.2	100.0
Total	45	100.0	100.0	

The following chart and table divided the customers among 3 categories only. 26.7% said that it is neutral that the laboratory staff provides solutions for them and

it might be because they're needless of that, while the majority 73.3% are strongly satisfied or satisfied by the solutions the staff always strive to provide for them.

Are you satisfied by the way the employees took you in charge?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid SDS	1	2.2	2.2	2.2
N	6	13.3	13.3	15.6
S	14	31.1	31.1	46.7
SS	24	53.3	53.3	100.0

Total	45	100.0	100.0	
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The neutral category in this table and chart was 13.3% regarding the customer satisfaction of how they were taking charge of by employees, while only 2.2% were

strongly dissatisfied. The majority are among satisfied (31.1%) and strongly satisfied (53.3%).

Do you inform the hospital about new ideas that you find helpful for you or other patients?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid SDS	9	20.0	20.0	20.0
DS	5	11.1	11.1	31.1
N	14	31.1	31.1	62.2
S	8	17.8	17.8	80.0
SS	9	20.0	20.0	100.0
Total	45	100.0	100.0	

Customers vary, as shown in this chart and table, among 5 categories pertaining to whether they inform the hospital about new ideas that they find helpful for

themselves or others. 20% are strongly dissatisfied, 11.1% are dissatisfied, 31.1% neutral, 17.8% are satisfied and 20% are strongly satisfied.

4.6.2 Customers' T-Test:

One-Sample Statistics

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
SAF4	Did the laboratory staff explain to you about the new online result tracking application?	45	4.2889	1.14062	.17003	25.224	44	.000
SAF5	Would you provide the hospital easily all the personal information needed?	45	4.4667	.96766	.14425	30.965	44	.000
SAF6	Are you satisfied with the new online result hospital tracking application?	45	3.3333	1.38170	.20597	16.183	44	.000
SAF7	Does the laboratory staff remind you about the date of tests that should be repeated?	45	3.1333	.94388	.14071	22.269	44	.000
SAF8	Do you think that the laboratory staff provides convenient solutions for your inquiry?	45	4.1556	.82450	.12291	33.810	44	.000
SAF9	Are you satisfied by the way the employees took you in charge?	45	4.3333	.87905	.13104	33.069	44	.000
SAF10	Do you inform the hospital about new ideas that you find helpful for you or other patients?	45	3.0667	1.38826	.20695	14.818	44	.000

Table 9: Customers' T-Test Results

N=45

SAF4:

Mean depression score ($M = 4.2$, $SD = 1.14$) was around or lower than the normal depression score of 4.0, $t(44) = 25.22$, $p = 0.000$.

SAF5:

Mean depression score ($M = 4.4$, $SD = 0.96$) was around or lower than the normal depression score of 4.0, $t(44) = 30.9$, $p = 0.000$.

SAF6:

Mean depression score ($M = 3.33$, $SD = 1.38$) was around or lower than the normal depression score of 4.0, $t(44) = 16.18$, $p = 0.000$.

SAF7:

Mean depression score ($M = 3.13$, $SD = 0.94$) was lower than the normal depression score of 4.0, $t(44) = 22.26$, $p = 0.000$.

SAF8:

Mean depression score ($M = 4.1$, $SD = 0.87$) was around or lower than the normal depression score of 4.0, $t(44) = 33.8$, $p = 0.000$.

SAF9:

Mean depression score ($M = 4.33$, $SD = 0.87$) was around or lower than the normal depression score of 4.0, $t(44) = 33.06$, $p = 0.000$.

SAF10:

Mean depression score ($M = 3.06$, $SD = 1.38$) was lower than the normal depression score of 4.0, $t(44) = 14.8$, $p = 0.000$.

Some Means are equal to 4 or slightly greater; this might be due to the sample size. Even though, we have a statistically significant difference between means ($p < .05$),

$p = 0.000$, thus, we can reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis.

4.6.3 Customers Correlation Table and Analysis:**Correlations**

		SAF4	SAF5	SAF6	SAF7	SAF8	SAF9	SAF10
SAF4	Pearson Correlation	1	.081	.601**	-.037	-.049	.196	.232
	Sig.		.597	.000	.811	.750	.196	.126
SAF5	Pearson Correlation	.081	1	.204	.129	.135	.454**	.179
	Sig.	.597		.179	.397	.377	.002	.239
SAF6	Pearson Correlation	.601**	.204	1	.000	-.047	.000	.462**
	Sig.	.000	.179		1.000	.761	1.000	.001
SAF7	Pearson Correlation	-.037	.129	.000	1	.206	.219	.340*
	Sig.	.811	.397	1.000		.174	.148	.022
SAF8	Pearson Correlation	-.049	.135	-.047	.206	1	.460**	.269
	Sig.	.750	.377	.761	.174		.001	.074
SAF9	Pearson Correlation	.196	.454**	.000	.219	.460**	1	.205
	Sig.	.196	.002	1.000	.148	.001		.177
SAF10	Pearson Correlation	.232	.179	.462**	.340*	.269	.205	1
	Sig.	.126	.239	.001	.022	.074	.177	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 10: Customers Correlation

There is positive correlation between:

- Between SAF4 and SAF6 equal to 0.601 at a significant level of $0.000 < 0.05$.
- Between SAF5 and SAF9 equal to 0.454 at a significant level of $0.002 < 0.05$.
- Between SAF6 and SAF10 equal to 0.462 at a significant level of $0.001 < 0.05$.
- Between SAF7 and SAF10 equal to 0.340 at a significant level of $0.022 < 0.05$.
- Between SAF8 and SAF9 equal to 0.460 at a significant level of $0.001 < 0.05$.

There are positive relations between:

- Explanation about the new online result application and by the staff and satisfaction of the customers about this application.
- How easily customers provide the laboratory their personal information and customers' satisfaction by the way the employees took in charge.
- Informing the hospital about new ideas that customers find it helpful for them or other patients and:

- Customers' satisfaction by the new online result tracking application
- The laboratory staff reminding their customers about the date of tests that should be repeated
- customer satisfaction by the way the employees took in charge and:
 - If customers think that the laboratory staff provides convenient solutions for their inquiry
 - How easily customers provide the laboratory their personal information

According to the correlation table we do not have any significant negative relation.

4.6.4 Customers' ANOVA Test Analysis:

ONEWAY BY SAFI

Descriptive

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Did the laboratory staff explain to you about the new online result tracking application?	Male	22	4.6364	.90214	.19234
	Female	23	3.9565	1.26053	.26284
	Total	45	4.2889	1.14062	.17003
Would you provide the hospital easily all the personal information needed?	Male	22	4.9545	.21320	.04545
	Female	23	4.0000	1.16775	.24349
	Total	45	4.4667	.96766	.14425
Are you satisfied with the new online result hospital tracking application?	Male	22	3.6818	1.28680	.27435
	Female	23	3.0000	1.41421	.29488
	Total	45	3.3333	1.38170	.20597
Does the laboratory staff remind you about the date of tests that should be repeated?	Male	22	3.4545	.73855	.15746
	Female	23	2.8261	1.02922	.21461
	Total	45	3.1333	.94388	.14071
Do you think that the laboratory staff provides convenient solutions for your inquiry?	Male	22	4.2727	.88273	.18820
	Female	23	4.0435	.76742	.16002
	Total	45	4.1556	.82450	.12291
Are you satisfied by the way the employees took you in charge?	Male	22	4.6818	.47673	.10164
	Female	23	4.0000	1.04447	.21779
	Total	45	4.3333	.87905	.13104
Do you inform the hospital about new ideas that you find helpful for you or other patients?	Male	22	3.4545	1.26217	.26910
	Female	23	2.6957	1.42812	.29778
	Total	45	3.0667	1.38826	.20695

Table 11: Descriptive table by SAFI

ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Did the laboratory staff explain to you about the new online result	Between Groups	5.197	1	5.197	4.294	.044
	Within Groups	52.047	43	1.210		

tracking application?	Total	57.244	44			
Would you provide the hospital easily all the personal information needed?	Between Groups	10.245	1	10.245	14.232	.000
	Within Groups	30.955	43	.720		
	Total	41.200	44			
Does the laboratory staff remind you about the date of tests that should be repeated?	Between Groups	4.441	1	4.441	5.494	.024
	Within Groups	34.759	43	.808		
	Total	39.200	44			
Are you satisfied by the way the employees took you in charge?	Between Groups	5.227	1	5.227	7.812	.008
	Within Groups	28.773	43	.669		
	Total	34.000	44			

Table 12: AOVA Test by SAF1

By analyzing the given ANOVA table, we find

- In the first question, the reported level of significance is $p = 0.044 < 0.05$ implying that the relation between CRM technology and life value through employee performance among all customers (as a dimension) is highly significant and it is safe to use CRMT in order to improve performance of laboratory.
- In the second question, the reported level of significance is $p = 0.000 < 0.05$ implying that the relation between CRM technology and satisfaction & loyalty through providing the hospital and laboratory all personal information needed easily which help the laboratory to understand their customers and shows confidence (as a dimension) is highly significant

and it is safe to use CRMT in order to improve performance of laboratory.

- In the third question, the reported level of significance is $p = 0.024 < 0.05$ implying that the relation between CRM technology and life value through understanding their customers' needs (as a dimension) is highly significant and it is safe to use CRMT in order to improve performance of laboratory.
- In the fourth question, the reported level of significance is $p = 0.008 < 0.05$ implying that the relation between CRM technology and life value through employees' performance (as a dimension) is highly significant and it is safe to use CRMT in order to improve performance of laboratory.

ONEWAY BY SAF2

Descriptive

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	
Did the laboratory staff explain to you about the new online result tracking application?	<30	16	4.0625	1.28938	.32234
	<50	20	4.4000	1.23117	.27530
	<70	9	4.4444	.52705	.17568
	Total	45	4.2889	1.14062	.17003
Would you provide the hospital easily all the personal information needed?	<30	16	4.3750	1.02470	.25617
	<50	20	4.5000	1.10024	.24602
	<70	9	4.5556	.52705	.17568
	Total	45	4.4667	.96766	.14425
Are you satisfied with the new online result hospital tracking application?	<30	16	2.9375	1.48183	.37046
	<50	20	3.7000	1.30182	.29110
	<70	9	3.2222	1.30171	.43390
	Total	45	3.3333	1.38170	.20597
Does the laboratory staff remind you about the date of tests that should be repeated?	<30	16	3.6250	.88506	.22127
	<50	20	3.0000	.56195	.12566
	<70	9	2.5556	1.33333	.44444
	Total	45	3.1333	.94388	.14071
Do you think that the laboratory staff provides convenient solutions for your inquiry?	<30	16	4.0000	.81650	.20412
	<50	20	4.3500	.81273	.18173
	<70	9	4.0000	.86603	.28868
	Total	45	4.1556	.82450	.12291
Are you satisfied by the way the employees took you in charge?	<30	16	4.3750	.71880	.17970
	<50	20	4.4500	.99868	.22331

	<70	9	4.0000	.86603	.28868
	Total	45	4.3333	.87905	.13104
	<30	16	2.8125	1.04682	.26171
Do you inform the hospital about new ideas that you find helpful for you or other patients?	<50	20	3.8500	1.18210	.26433
	<70	9	1.7778	1.30171	.43390
	Total	45	3.0667	1.38826	.20695

Table 13: Descriptive table by SAF2

ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Do you inform the hospital about new ideas that you find helpful for you or other patients?	Between Groups	28.257	2	14.128	10.495	.000
	Within Groups	56.543	42	1.346		
	Total	84.800	44			

Table 14: ANOVA Test By SAF2

By analyzing the given ANOVA table, it is found that the reported level of significance is $p = 0.000 < 0.05$ implying that the relation between CRM technology and loyalty & satisfaction through

providing ideas (as a dimension) is highly significant and it is safe to use CRMT in order to improve performance of laboratory.

ONEWAY BY SAF3

Descriptive

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Did the laboratory staff explain to you about the new online result tracking application?	First time	2	5.0000	.00000	.00000
	sometimes	12	3.5000	1.56670	.45227
	mostly	16	4.2500	1.00000	.25000
	Always	15	4.8667	.35187	.09085
	Total	45	4.2889	1.14062	.17003
Would you provide the hospital easily all the personal information needed?	First time	2	4.5000	.70711	.50000
	sometimes	12	4.1667	.83485	.24100
	mostly	16	4.3125	1.35247	.33812
	Always	15	4.8667	.35187	.09085
	Total	45	4.4667	.96766	.14425
Are you satisfied with the new online result hospital tracking application?	First time	2	3.0000	.00000	.00000
	sometimes	12	3.1667	1.33712	.38599
	mostly	16	2.9375	1.48183	.37046
	Always	15	3.9333	1.27988	.33046
	Total	45	3.3333	1.38170	.20597
Does the laboratory staff remind you about the date of tests that should be repeated?	First time	2	3.0000	.00000	.00000
	sometimes	12	2.8333	1.33712	.38599
	mostly	16	3.0000	.63246	.15811
	Always	15	3.5333	.83381	.21529
	Total	45	3.1333	.94388	.14071
Do you think that the laboratory staff provides convenient solutions for your inquiry?	First time	2	3.0000	.00000	.00000
	sometimes	12	3.8333	.83485	.24100
	mostly	16	4.1875	.75000	.18750
	Always	15	4.5333	.74322	.19190
	Total	45	4.1556	.82450	.12291
Are you satisfied by the way the employees took you in charge?	First time	2	4.0000	.00000	.00000
	sometimes	12	3.8333	.83485	.24100
	mostly	16	4.2500	1.06458	.26615
	Always	15	4.8667	.35187	.09085

	Total	45	4.3333	.87905	.13104
	First time	2	1.5000	.70711	.50000
Do you inform the hospital about new ideas that you find helpful for you or other patients?	sometimes	12	2.5000	1.16775	.33710
	mostly	16	3.1250	1.36015	.34004
	Always	15	3.6667	1.39728	.36078
	Total	45	3.0667	1.38826	.20695

Table 15: Descriptive table by SAF3

ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Did the laboratory staff explain to you about the new online result tracking application?	Between Groups	13.511	3	4.504	4.222	.011
	Within Groups	43.733	41	1.067		
	Total	57.244	44			
Do you think that the laboratory staff provides convenient solutions for your inquiry?	Between Groups	6.074	3	2.025	3.482	.024
	Within Groups	23.838	41	.581		
	Total	29.911	44			
Are you satisfied by the way the employees took you in charge?	Between Groups	7.600	3	2.533	3.934	.015
	Within Groups	26.400	41	.644		
	Total	34.000	44			

Table 16: AOVA Test by SAF3

By analyzing the given ANOVA table, we find:

- In the first question, that the reported level of significance is $p= 0.011 < 0.05$ implying that the relation between CRM technology and life value through employee performance (as a dimension) is highly significant and it is safe to use CRMT in order to improve performance of laboratory.
- In the second question, the reported level of significance is $p= 0.024 < 0.05$ implying that the relation between CRM technology and satisfaction & loyalty through employee

performance and providing solutions for their customers (as a dimension) is highly significant and it is safe to use CRMT in order to improve performance of laboratory.

- In the third question, that the reported level of significance is $p= 0.015 < 0.05$ implying that the relation between CRM technology and life value through employee performance (as a dimension) is highly significant and it is safe to use CRMT in order to improve performance of laboratory.

4.7 Interview’s answers:

- 1- Can you explain the “Tracking Results Online” procedure and why it was adopted?
 “Tracking results online is an application connected to the internet containing a database with every customer test in our laboratory. The patient receives a code number which allows him to receive his result online without the need to come to the laboratory. The advantage of this application is that the results are ready to be used for any formal needs like Social Security Corporation or Insurance companies. The idea comes from considering the information we collected about patient’s job situation, residence, and the security situation of each customer.”
- 2- Was your staff trained on the CRMS before the laboratory started implementing it?

“Yes, all the staff was trained prior because everyone here is directly related to the system through different ways.”

- 3- Guide me through the journey a typical customer goes through from the moment he enters the laboratory?
 “Customers here are patients and our service concerns their health. Most of the patients come with psychological worries which affect them negatively, here is where the patient’s trip begins. The first stage is the secretary department where factorizing and coding of each patient is completed. Coding means providing each patient with a fixed file number and different code for each time the patient tests in our laboratory. Afterwards, they collect the samples needed and sort them by labeling them with the code of each test. The second stage is to

put samples in the machine, after which the machine will read the code of the test as well as the code of the patient and start testing it. This machine is linked to the system, so it sends the results to it directly. The third stage is validation stage, here 2 validations should be approved “Technical validation and Biological validation.” When they are approved, the results will be ready to be connected online were they can be printed out directly. If not online, patients can come to the laboratory with their code and take them by hand.”

4- Can your customers use the online results to print a second copy for formal use?

“No, if they want the results for a second time, they should come to the laboratory to obtain them.”

5- Do all your customers obtain their results online?

“Till this date, no because some patients prefer to take their results by hand. For some it is because they need reassurance from our staff regarding the results if they are worried, need information regarding their follow up appointment with their doctor like checking whether it is delayed for example, or lack the technological knowledge.”

6- Is CRMS connected to all departments of the laboratory? If no why?

“Actually no, only the Bacteriology department is still done manually and not directly connected. We need new machine to integrate it with our online application and purchasing this machine needs more space, staff, and budget. This is our new project we are preparing for.”

7- Are all laboratory tests done locally or do you need to send some to other laboratories?

“Regarding with most patients’ needs, all are done locally, however there are about 12% of tests, that are rare to be demanded like “Bahjat disease” and some genetic tests, which are sent to other local and foreign laboratories.”

8- What do you anticipate is required to be able to test everything in your laboratory?

“We need a new machine, but for the next 10 years I don’t anticipate that we will purchase it because of its big price and the huge space it needs, and as I told you it is rate to have patients whom need this test, and can be sent to other laboratories which we trust.”

9- Do you think that the CRMS and the Tracking Results Online application improve the performance of the laboratory and thus customer loyalty?

“Through CRMS we were able to understand how hard it is for our customers to come more than once to the laboratory because of their work or concerns and the distance. Another reason for tracking this application is that it reduces time and reduces errors by depending more on sophisticated machines. Therefore, we worked on the development and implementation of this application which is really admired by our customers and was a platform to increase the number of new customers. I can tell you that CRMS and the tracking online system increased our customers the first year by 6%. The Laboratory and Haykal hospital believe that customers deserve a lot of services to benefit from directly by noticing and using them.”

As a conclusion of this interview, it can be analyzed that appreciating customers and analyzing their collected information allows an organization to improve its performance toward their customers. In addition to that, a main point was mentioned which is to allow customers to notice your performance by direct use of the services submitted. When the customers directly benefit from the service and understand its importance, their satisfaction will increase and they will be at the organizations defense in face of any social bashing in the society

4.6 Conclusion of the Chapter:

As a conclusion from the mean test, it was found that all five dimensions are considered to be significant with

reported $p < 0.05$. Therefore, all the five dimensions are considered to be general critical attributes that can strongly contribute to the success of CRM Technology within Haykal Laboratory. Furthermore, all laboratories must focus on ensuring the availability of all such critical aspects within their work environments to assure the success of the CRMT concept. The following table exposes the accepted hypotheses for this study.

Hypotheses	Path	Level of significance	Results
H1	DT& TD → CRMT	0.004** 0.038**	Supported
H2	CSAL → CRMT	0.000**	Supported

		0.000** 0.024**	
H3	LLF → CRMT	0.024** 0.008** 0.011** 0.015**	Supported

Table 17: Accepted Hypothesis

DT & TD: Data Collected & Take Decision

CSAL: Customer Satisfaction & Loyalty

LLV: Long Life Value

As previously mentioned, the model built for this study was based on important characteristics that contribute to the performance of any organization especially in the health care sector through the CRM System implementation. Those characteristics were investigated throughout literature as critical elements to succeed within industry, as well as, considered by literature as critical components to assure a long-life value. And by applying the entire study on Haykal laboratory, the results revealed that there are five critical attributes that can result in successful CRMS implementation within organizations. The five critical attributes, listed above, were furthermore approved through literature studies as important contributors.

Thus, the entire study approved that data collected and understanding customers' needs support organization by creating a platform base in order to make the right decision and take the right actions in order to directly solve customer problems. This facilitation that aids employees to provide convenient solutions for customers will build good relationship between an organization and customers that will, in return, increase the level of satisfaction and loyalty. Thus, the posed characteristics will lead to achieving planned organization goals and objectives efficiently and increasing the long-life value of the organization among the industry.

Utilizing a CRMS is considered among the most important contributors to successful organization and long-life value. Furthermore, studies conducted through literature on CRM System implied that the existence of such system within the work environment results in employees feeling significant, productive, right decision takers, as well as high loyalty and satisfaction to the organization. Also, several studies mentioned through literature that deal with the concept of CRMS implementation, that providing an organization with data and a CRM system empowers employees and managers to seek solutions by their own efforts for their customers aiming to take the right decision and eliminate or lessen errors which will increase customers' loyalty and satisfaction.

Finally, rewarding employees for achieving intended organization goals and objectives efficiently is another important contributor to CRMS implementation which also leads to long life value

Chapter Five: Conclusion and Recommendation

5.1 Conclusion

From the results of demographic data, it's apparent that the majority of employees are greater than 30 years and the majority of them imply that their organizations implement CRMS necessity. Most of the employees have experience of more than 5 years. Additionally, most of the employees ensure that they have received equipment and training needed. Furthermore, when employees were asked about their opinion about CRMS implementation within their job, the results were positive and optimistic. Most of them believe that their tasks cannot be achieved without CRMS and that CRMS improves their performance, reduces errors, and increases return rate through understanding customers' needs via data collected about them. This implies that the Haykal Laboratory employees perceive the importance of implementation of CRMS within their organization and ensure it's vital. Moreover, the majority of employees are mid-aged adults with a year of good experience. This makes them more welcome to any new training within their organization, including the updated systems needed to be implemented of CRM. Hence, Haykal laboratory employees support the need for CRMS implementation within the hospital and imply the most serious characteristics that contribute to the successful CRMS implementation.

From the results of demographic data, it's obvious that most of customers differ among variant ages. Correspondingly, the majority of the customers mentioned that the staff of the laboratory explained the new online result tracking application to them and they were satisfied by it. However, some clients still prefer to take their results by hand, possibly due to their age and lack of knowledge about technology. Most of the customers have experienced other laboratories, however,

when they were asked about their dealing with the Haykal laboratory, the results were positive and optimistic. Most patients deal with Haykal laboratory mostly and provide staff with any information needed easily and without embarrassment, as a result of the staffs' outstanding performance and the convenient solutions provided to the patients, leading them to feel satisfied which, in return, increases the organization's long life value level. This implies that the Haykal Laboratory's customers perceive the importance of implementation of CRMS without understanding it directly as a system and ensure it's important.

In regards to the management of hospital and laboratory, appreciating customers and making them one of the main visions services them to collect and analyze more data in order to improve decisions, satisfy needs, and improve performance of the organization overall. One of the main aspects in the CRM world that needs to be focused on furthermore is the importance of customers' direct benefit and usage of the service of CRMS submitted in order to reach the organizational goal of increasing loyalty and life value.

Thus, the entire study approved that data collected and understanding customers' needs improve an organization by giving employees responsibility to take the most possible good decisions and actions in order to solve problems directly for customers. This expedition and the direct customers' usage of CRMS service submitted will help employees to provide convenient solutions for customers and build good relationship with them. This will increase the level of satisfaction and loyalty. Thus, the resulted characteristics will lead to achieving planned organization goals and objectives efficiently as well as increase the long-life value of the organization among the industry.

5.2 Recommendations

It is vital for any organization, especially hospitals, to put the critical success aspects for CRM System implementation in set. Doing so will require them to undertake wide changes in the workflow and improve organization performance. Moreover, hospitals must focus on improving their CRM system to include

other programs that can indeed connect more with customers who must benefit directly from this system. An organization must also motivate employees, increase their productivity, and reduce errors in order to increase customer satisfaction.

In respect, all managers and employees should have the opportunity to benefit from this system in order to achieve job satisfaction and motivation visualized through the increasing the level of perfection and reducing errors. Implementing the CRM system such that it is used by all employees throughout the organization gives the organization the greatest opportunity to increase creativity in taking decision, flexibility in collecting and using data, feasibility in understanding their customers, and responsibility in increasing customer loyalty and life value of the organization which are all results of successful CRM system implementation.

5.3 Study Limitations

The first study limitation is that the time and number of respondents as customers was insufficient to acquire more accurate results which can be generalized. Likewise, the number of employees was not large and sufficient. One of the main limitations is the incapability of assembling an interview with the laboratory manager. Another limitation is that the entire model chooses to study one hospital for CRM system implementation within its area. Similarly, the literature provided many other factors that are also considered essential for successful CRM system implementation but were not discussed due to time limitations.

5.4 Further Studies

The future direction of this study is to assess the other critical aspects that contribute to the success of CRM system implementation within organizations which the study was not able to cover. Another future direction, is to study how these critical aspects must be implemented and what changes should be done in the organization to maintain the successful of CRM system implementation within the entire organization environment.

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